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D 5.2 Visual Identity Handbook

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Partners short names

ENVI	Parco Scientifico Tecnologico Per L'ambiente Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrogeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodoroden Klaster

Executive Summary

This document introduces the communication and dissemination project's materials, as well as the HYPOP visual identity. It is a complementary document to the D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan for a practical definition of the communication and dissemination efforts of the HYPOP Consortium throughout the duration of the project.

Aims and scope of dissemination, communication and exploitation are different, according to the official glossary of the European Commission (EC):

1. **Communication:** these measures should promote the project throughout the full lifespan of the project. The aim is to inform, reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and benefits the project will have for citizens;
2. **Dissemination:** the public disclosure of the results (e.g. any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected) by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium;
3. **Exploitation:** the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

Dissemination, communication and exploitation Plan has been developed during the first months of the project and it is integrated under WP5 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. APRE's team, as WP5 leader, will be responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present Visual Identity Handbook and will develop the main tools and materials to be used during the project. The present document outlines:

- Objectives of the strategy;
- Target audiences and respective dissemination and communication objectives;
- HYPOP brand identity and Communication Kit;
- Main dissemination and communication tools and channels to reach the audiences;
- Main activities including an indicative timeline for their implementation;
- A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), barriers and obstacles considered to reach KPIs.

All partners will also be actively involved in the dissemination and communication actions implementation and are highly committed to ensure a satisfactory dissemination of the project's results. The expected contributions from partners are to:

- Implement promotional and dissemination campaigns in their own countries and at European level
- Exploit their contacts and networks
- Supply news and updates for the web portal and newsletter
- Interact with the project's posts on various Social Media Channels
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes.

1 Introduction

HYPOP - HYdrOgen Public OPiniOn and accePtance is a project is funded by the Clean Hydrogen JU and its members and co-founded by the European Union under Grant Agreement number No 10111193.

HYPOP main objective is to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through:

- a) the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of H2 technologies.
- b) the creation of a web platform collecting communication material, mainly videos, on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities.

HYPOP is led by ENVI, an innovation accelerator for business with 20 years' experience in the hydrogen sector. HYPOP is represented by a well-balanced Consortium representing 6 Countries: National Hydrogen Clusters (IT, B, PL, BG), three Research Organisations (IR, ES), an Agency for the Promotion of European Research (IT).

Four guidelines will be developed: one more public oriented that will report on best practices to involve citizens, the other 3 collecting the results coming from the involvement of stakeholders' groups (First Responders, Permitting Authorities, Certification Body). HYPOP will also contribute to the definition of indicators to be used for Social Life Cycle Assessment of hydrogen technologies, and for this will focus on 2 applications: residential and mobility, which will enter into the daily life of people. HYPOP will also be connected with some ongoing H2 projects characterised by demonstration activities in public spaces. Some of them have already been identified, i.e., Everywh2ere, Reflex, H2Ports, REMOTE: they are well known to the consortium partners and have faced some barriers often due to a lack of specific reference cases for the authorities called upon to grant safety and other permissions for the installation or use of the demonstrators. The HYPOP website aims to become the hosting site of similar videos explaining upcoming hydrogen technology currently under development and demonstration.

2 Objectives of the Handbook

The main objective of the Visual Identity Handbook of the HYPOP project is to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities and timelines on how/when/where to disseminate the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (corporate websites, social networks, etc.) to support the dissemination, with the following goals:

- Raise awareness on the project activities and events
- Communicate and disseminate results achieved among HYPOP target groups
- Identify and use the right channels to efficiently communicate with the target groups and stakeholders (including the identification of events, social media networks, press releases, multiplier organisations, etc.)
- Produce the necessary supporting material to ensure an effective dissemination, including printed material (i.e. brochure, poster, roll-up) and digital materials (videos, infographics)
- Facilitate regular communication, through press releases and newsletters, to inform about the latest news and developments of the project to the media
- Identify potential ways for ensuring all projects outcomes beyond the duration of the project.

3 The Handbook

The strategy of this Visual Identity Handbook focuses on establishing realistic dissemination and communication activities in line with the progress of the project and the utilization of appropriate tools, channels and formats to communicate with the target audiences in a defined timeline. The document is complementary to the First Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy as defined in Deliverable 5.1.

To achieve dissemination and communication objectives in a timely and adequate manner, HYPOP consortium will follow the roadmap below:

Activity	Time plan	Description
Planning	M1-M4	Identify the communication and dissemination strategy to ensure a wide outreach of project's outcomes
Implementation	M4-M24	Produce a set of tools (supports and channels) to diffuse key messages extracted from the project results to the identified target groups
Monitoring	M4-M24	Analyse and assess the impact and success of dissemination and communication activities by comparing the results to the pre-established key performance indicators (KPIs)
Sustainability	M20-M24	Identify and establish mechanisms needed to ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility of HYPOP outcomes

Table 1:HYPOP communication and dissemination roadmap

3.1 Target Groups

The HYPOP project envisages the engagement of the following target groups:

- first target group encompasses citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyse the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes first responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

The abovementioned Target Groups will be better defined by the analysis performed in WP1 (as per Grant Agreement) and WP2.

Find in the table below a further description of the involved target groups:

Target group	Description
Citizens	Samples from 6 countries with different hydrogen social acceptance, different age, gender and sociocultural background. The analysis conducted will also integrate other states not HYPOP partners.
Manufacturers/Hydrogen Sector	Providers and industries representatives from FCH technologies, specifically focus on residential, energy and transport sectors (synergies with other projects).
HYPOP identified stakeholders	First responders (at least from HYPOP 6 Countries), Permitting's entities (at least from HYPOP 6 Countries), Certification Body (AENOR as AB, at least 3 others).
Public Authorities/Decision Makers	Local, regional, and national decision makers (at least 10).
EU and local projects	European and not European projects (10), focused on hydrogen research and its application.
Clusters, territorial associations, networks, hydrogen valley	Organizations working at territorial level and gathering figures from the same sectors (HYPOP project: ENVI, CNH2, RIGP. Tweed, BH2C + at least 5 territorial associations as H2IT and at least 3 Hydrogen Valley) or interested to create collaboration and enhance the local community growth.
Experts on Hydrogen and Communication	Technical or other figures working in hydrogen development projects, internal figures in the project or experts in communication (journalists, social media managers, press).
Scientific Community	Experts and scientist on hydrogen technologies, social aspects and technological innovation.

Table 2: Target Groups description

HYPOP's Teams will engage (WP3 and WP4) specific Citizen and Stakeholder categories (see table below):

Citizen and Stakeholder categories	Key engagement	HYPPOP Hub - Web Platform	Social Media	Expert Forum	Planned Events	Publication Repository	Workshops (co creation) Webinars	EU Technology pathway	Video/Infographics	Other Communication
Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)	Acceptance of citizens is needed for a technology uptake. CSOS will reinforce representativeness of their sectors/thematic focus for the benefit their members	X	X		X		X		X	
Experts from research/academia	HYPOP will increase the hydrogen technologies visibility through promotion in experts' webinars, workshop, conference, podcasts, etc., and to increase knowledge-sharing with and between these stakeholders	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations	These stakeholders will give first-end information on hydrogen technologies as they are early adopters/up-takers of new emerging technologies	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EU, national and regional policy bodies,	Public authorities and specifically									

governmental institutions, innovation agencies	decision makers of hydrogen technologies will be continuously targeted to be informed and familiarized with the concepts of enabling technologies	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Other initiatives and projects	These stakeholders contribute to community building through cross-pollination and fertilization in order to increase synergies and networks	X	X			X			X	X

Table 3: Citizens and Stakeholders categories

4 Brand Identity

The brand identity of a project consists of a set of elements that forms its graphic individuality.

APRE developed an initial visual identity for HYPOP project by M3, together with the dissemination and communication toolkit (Annex to this deliverable), deliverable and presentation’s template and communication materials.

4.1 Logo

The project logo has been designed by a professional designer. The logo has been designed to be easily recognisable and is composed of elements representing the core aspects of HYPOP: emerging enabling technologies.

A baseline can be added to specify the project aim.

The logo with baseline is as follows:

Different versions of the HYPOP logo have been produced, adapted to different backgrounds and displays (screen, print, white background, etc.). The logo is available both in pixel and vector formats and is available for the partners' use via the project shared platform on SharePoint.

All the different options for the logo can be found in Annex 11.1.2 in this document.

4.2 Brand Manual

After the final logo was chosen, APRE created a brand manual (Annex 11.1.1), which was distributed to all partners with the aim of providing them with guidelines on how to best use the logo, the specific font, colours and dimensions, as well as examples of logo applications on various materials.

4.3 Claim

The claim is a sentence that wants to emphasize the main core of the project and catch immediately the attention of people, with the goal of providing initial engagement and curiosity. After analysing different alternatives, the chosen claim for HYPOP is “*Let's make the hydrogen revolution*”.

The claim has been identified to catch audiences' attention with a short and direct message, that encourages the reader to find out more and to take action.

5 Tools and Channels

The achievement of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy objectives will be ensured by the complementarity of its component activities. These will guarantee both project dissemination and constant and/or specific feedback from stakeholders.

APRE will manage and ensure the ongoing synergy between the activities to make the most out of the content produced within the project, by communicating the knowledge in different styles (infographics, videos, images, etc) for different platforms (website, social networks, etc). Therefore, several tools and channels will be used to support the communication of the right messages to the targeted audiences as presented below.

5.1 Website

The first version of the HYPOP website (splash page) has been launched in October 2023 (M5), the full website is running since November 2023 (M6) at the URL: <https://www.hypop-project.eu/>.

The website acts as the main portal for HYPOP's editorial content, its engagement activities and all related events in which partners will participate.

All website contents will be reviewed by APRE taking into account SEO (Search Engine Optimization) best practices for a better indexation and accessibility of the project via Internet.

Additionally, the project will use Google Analytics 4 for web analytics service to track website traffic and assess useful statistics that will help to optimize the website and the communication and dissemination strategy. Relevant statistics that will be monitored are:

- Unique visitors;
- Total visitors;
- Which links and countries the web traffic comes from;
- Number of download of documents (public results, communication kit, newsletters).

The website is also the entry point for any interested user: the page 'Join our community' is an open form where the user can fill in with contact details for join:

- Project's Newsletter to be informed about the project's outcomes;
- Project's Database which will results in: invitation to events and workshops; relevant activities and initiatives implemented in the context of clean hydrogen EU projects in which HYPOP consortium is involved;

The policy privacy is compliant with the EU Regulation 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR") as indicated in the webpage: <https://www.hypop-project.eu/privacy-policy/>

Structure of the website is detailed in Annex 11.1.3.

The following KPIs will be used to monitor and measure website activities:

- N. of website online (M6): **1**
- N. of total visits: **> 15.000**
- N. of countries reached **>27**

5.2 Social Network

HYPOP will maintain an active presence online through the use of five major social media platforms: LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube. The main objective of maintaining a relevant online presence is to reach and engage as many stakeholders as possible (with a special attention to generic public) thanks to a findable and recognizable production of contents. All the profiles are active since M6.

The different types of social networks used have been deemed appropriate to reach specific target groups, and likewise the content disseminated will also depend on these groups and channels. The same applies for paid campaigns launched for the promotion of specific initiatives or results, which will be tailored based on contents and the target audience and agreed in synergy with the Consortium.

All the social media channels will be used also to gather information and needs for the social awareness goal of the project, using a bottom-up approach.

5.2.1 Workflow

APRE set a specific workflow for Social Network (SN) publications.

By the 10th of every month (to be postponed to the first working day available in case of holidays), partners can send to APRE their inputs (via the excel file available online on the project repository) about tasks implementation and results, but also about relevant news regarding HYPOP framework (activities performed, events attended, etc.). Thanks to these inputs, APRE can setup a draft of the editorial plan for the month ahead.

In addition to partners' suggestions, APRE will prepare posts about: partners' organization and their roles in the project, short interviews to the main target stakeholders about challenges and solutions, coordinated contents with other EU projects and initiatives and national target stakeholders.

8 different cards will be produced every month with original contents and re-share of relevant events or initiatives.

5.2.2 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn HYPOP page will be used in order to increase the visibility of the project at a professional and academic level. LinkedIn gives networking opportunities for professionals and members, while creating links between different working groups and projects.

LinkedIn also offers the possibility to reach many business and policy stakeholders and therefore plays a key role in the communication activities of the project.

5.2.3 Twitter/X

Twitter/X can reach a wider and more heterogeneous audience, and will be used mainly for resharing and collaborations with other EU funded projects. It will be used with more frequency than other channels to post comments and news about the achievements and progress of the project and to promote project reports and participation in events.

Twitter/X will also be used to generate debates about the benefits and advantages of using clean hydrogen as an energy source.

5.2.4 Facebook

Facebook will be used with the goal of engaging and involving a large audience, especially among citizens and civil society, on the topic of hydrogen as a clean hydrogen source.

In this regard Facebook will be used as a tool to create an active community through themed posts, to promote events and fairs on the topic and to narrate the steps of the project.

5.2.5 Instagram

Instagram offers, due to its features, the possibility to create visual contents based on engaging graphics and videos. During the HYPOP project, it will be used to reach a younger portion of the civil society and share with them facts and information on hydrogen through the sharing of pictures and videos. Given the target chosen for this SN, the tone of the speech will be less formal and the type of post will attract more attention.

5.2.6 YouTube

YouTube is a popular video sharing website where registered users can upload and share videos with anyone being able to view them, even without registering an account, it is an excellent platform to save project videos, in order to share them with a broad audience.

Targeted audiences will receive specific messages – through emailing, other social media channels, website news, in direct exchange – to invite them to watch the videos HYPOP will place on YouTube. As such, YouTube will be a “repository” platform for HYPOP.

The HYPOP’s YouTube account will be created once the first project video has been developed, likely to happen within the first project year.

In order to reach all potential stakeholders, a set of videos will be developed using the following criteria:

- provide a general and short HYPOP project presentation
- understanding of hydrogen: how the technology works, which are the benefits, climatic impacts, applications, etc.
- promote/highlight specific activities and results of the project (e.g., co-creation workshops, etc.)
- illustrates the results and impacts created by the project (e.g. citizen acceptance, etc.).

The table below illustrates the KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) for activities related to social media channels:

Social media channels	Target	Audience
LinkedIn and Twitter/X	N. of LinkedIn/X followers: Y1: 700 Y2: 1000	Scientific experts, Industry, academia

Facebook	N. of Facebook followers: Y1: 200 Y2: 350	Civil society, communities, citizens, hydrogen groups
Instagram	N. of Instagram followers: Y1: 1000 Y2: 1500	Communities, citizens, younger audiences
YouTube	N. of YouTube followers: Y1: 300 Y2: 600	Communities, citizens, younger audiences

Table 4: Social media channels and KPIs

5.3 Newsletter

The Consortium foresees the production of 3 newsletters during the project, whose purpose will be to raise awareness of the project and its results, carry out its awareness raising campaign, and share project news. These newsletters will be sent proactively to the target audience identified, but it will also be possible for interested parties to subscribe via the HYPOP website.

HYPOP Partners will use their networks to encourage newsletter subscription and ensure the dissemination of this communication activity.

The KPIs foreseen for this activity are as follows:

Metrics	KPI
Download from the website	Download: >3000
Reach of each partner mailing	Reach: >20.000

Table 5: KPIs for newsletter

5.4 Events

A number of project events, such as workshops, conferences, webinars events are planned in the frame of HYPOP, either online or as physical gatherings in order to allow the partners to meet on a regular basis and to exchange with the target groups, present project ideas and findings and collect

feedback. They will also aim at a knowledge and information exchange with the key expert stakeholders.

These physical events shall, wherever possible and relevant, be organised in conjunction with a relevant external event (conference), in order to allow for synergies with the event participants and content.

5.4.1 Co-creation on line workshops

Dedicated online public engagement co-creation workshops will be organized by HYPOP Team in order to involve citizens, specialist, researchers, and other target groups. The aim of the workshops will be to involve citizens in the project activities and topics.

In addition to informing about the project, the project team plans to ask participants to reflect on their expectations for hydrogen in future settings (use, green impacts, carbon free vision, etc.)

The planning for the workshops is as follows:

- one workshop per country (at least 20 participants per country, three-hour duration)
- two international events (at least 50 participants per event, one/two-hour duration).

Skilled facilitators will encourage group interactions to capture relevant data and to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the group discussions. In particular, the HYPOP Team will prepare the guidelines and the good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of the Hydrogen Technologies.

5.4.2 Stakeholders engagement workshop

The aim of the workshops is inform and present, to the stakeholders, the main results related to the hydrogen acceptance requirements.

- In particular, identifying for each Country:
 - safety approaches and barriers;
 - certification rules;
 - regulation and standard procedures (hydrogen transportation, storage, use, etc.).

The final aim is to create main requirements road maps in hydrogen technologies implementation.

- The planning foresees:
 - workshop (on line, 4 hours duration) per each project country
 - final international event (in presence) near Clean Hydrogen Partnership headquarter (Brussels)

5.4.3 Outreach through other events

In addition to the events organised by HYPOP, project partners will take the opportunity for communicating about the project developments towards specific/specialised stakeholders during events they organise in another frame or during external events they attend (international conference).

It is expected that partners will present the project, activities and outcomes in conferences they will be attending throughout the duration of the project, use the opportunities for awareness raising, making use of communication material such as the flyers, as well as creating connections and thus nourishing the HYPOP community over time.

5.5 Other projects, synergies, and networks for collaboration

To maximise both regional and EU-wide visibility, and enhance long-term synergies, the HYPOP partners will actively work on establishing relationships with strategic EU actors.

The project's impacts will be amplified through networking activities with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, starting from the ones in which partners are involved (e.g., GREEN HYSLAND, H2Ports, EVERYWH2ERE, etc.).

Furthermore, APRE will map all the relevant projects and initiatives (clustering) and will contact all the stakeholders to establish a collaboration on the project's activities.

Where possible, synergies will also be created with organisations that have endorsed the project.

The overall aim of the networking and exchange around synergies will be to raise awareness within relevant target groups, to engage relevant actors into the project activities, and to serve common goals, broadening as such the impact of HYPOP and the initiatives it will be collaborating with.

6 Tools and channel

In the following table, it is possible to find a breakdown of the engagement of each target group foreseen for each communication tool and channel.

Tools and channels	Target groups						
	Policy makers	Educational organizations	Businesses	Civil society	Scientific communities	Other hydrogen projects and initiatives	Other region networks, intermediate organisations
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Communication kit (flyer, poster, rollups)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Twitter, LinkedIn	X	X	X		X	X	X
Facebook, Instagram		X	X	X		X	
Newsletter	X	X		X	X		X
Youtube, Videos		X	X	X	X	X	X
Conferences	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 6: engagement of target groups for each communication tool and channel

7 HYPOP and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

7.1 Key Performance Indicators

A Performance indicator represents a standard set to establish what the successful outcome of a task should be, in terms of impact, on the economy/society beyond those directly affected by the project activities¹.

A set of KPIs is defined in the Grant Agreement in order to assess the implementation of the Strategy every 12 months. KPIs will enable APRE to correct and adapt the strategy (through a dedicated section within periodic report at M18), considering also new emerging needs or external factors affecting the project.

KPIs are built considering ones contained in the Grant Agreement and new ones introduced in the first months of the project.

In the yearly assessment, the KPIs table will be updated with a column showing the progresses. Besides the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) listed in the table below, a number of project activities naturally feed into the communication and dissemination work: for example activities conducted in the gap analysis, workshops, reports, etc.

The monitoring will be based on the expected outcomes specified in section 1.

#	KPI	Target	Audience
1	HYPOP's visual identity and related promotional	N. of brand identity kit released: 1 N. of social media banners: 2 N. of flyers: 2	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon 2020 indicators : assessing the results and impact of Horizon, Publications Office, 2015, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/71098>

		<p>N. of roll-ups: 2</p> <p>N. of informative posters >2</p> <p>N. of flyers distributed >2000</p> <p>N. of newsletters produced: 3</p>	
2	Design infographics and develop informative videos	<p>N. of informative videos to explain hydrogen and its application translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >3</p> <p>N. of infographics to visualise project's outputs translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >5</p>	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large
3	Website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, Facebook, X, Instagram)	<p>Website:</p> <p>N. of website online (M4): 1</p> <p>N. of total visits: > 15.000</p> <p>N. of countries reached >27</p> <p>Social media:</p> <p>N. of accounts setup and active (M6): 5</p> <p>N. of posts per year (total): >50</p> <p>N. of social media campaigns: >5</p> <p>N. of LinkedIn/X followers: Y1: 700 Y2: 1000</p>	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large

		<p>N. of Facebook followers: Y1: 200 Y2: 350</p> <p>N. of Instagram followers: Y1: 1000 Y2: 1500</p> <p>YouTube viewers: Y1: n° 300 Y2: n° 600</p> <p>N. of general local event per country participated by the local partner): >1</p> <p>N. of article/radio or tv interviews in national or regional media by local partners for each partner country: >1</p>	
4	Participation in external events and conferences and promotion through traditional media channels (*)	<p>N. of participation in events with dedicated booths: >3</p> <p>N. of speeches at events and conferences (live and online): >5</p> <p>N. of articles in newspapers, magazines or radio: >8</p> <p>N. of press releases (to 10.000 + contacts): >6</p>	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large

5	Interconnection with hydrogen demo-project	N. of joint activities, demonstration event: 4	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large
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Table 7: HYPOP KPIs for communication and dissemination activities

(*):

Conference:

<https://conferenceindex.org/conferences/hydrogen> (List of Hydrogen Conference 2023/2024/2025)

<https://www.setac.org/discover-events/global-meetings.html> (SETAC Europe 35th Annual Meeting, expected in May 2025)

<https://www.iahe.org/whcwhctc.asp> (11th World Hydrogen Technology Convention, Dublin, 2025)

<https://euhydrogenweek.eu/> (Hydrogen Week 2023/2024)

<https://www.pollutec.com/en-gb/cometopollutecadwb.html> (POLLUTEC FAIR, Lyon, France, October 2023/2024, Participation with a booth this year)

H2 Day, organised by Environment Park once a year with its company cluster. Next one on 26th of October 2023

<https://www.ecomondo.com/> (ECOMONDO Fair (Rimini, Italy), once a year)

<https://interactive.eusew.eu/> (EUSEW Brussels. Once a year)

<https://hydrogen-uk.org/annual-conference-and-awards/> (11th,12th March - Hydrogen UK Annual Conference & Awards 2024)

<https://www.wheccancun.org/tracks> (23th-27th June - World Hydrogen Energy Conference)

<https://www.europe.gh2events.com/registration> (25th -27th June - Connecting Green Hydrogen Europe)

https://waset.org/hydrogen-energy-and-fuel-cells-technology-conference-in-september-2024-in-malaga?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing (6th-7th September - ICHEFCT 2024: 18. International Conference on Hydrogen Energy and Fuel Cells Technology)

https://waset.org/fuel-cells-hydrogen-energy-technology-and-applications-conference-in-december-2024-in-amsterdam?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing (2nd-3rd December - International Conference on Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Energy Technology and Applications)

Hydrogen Principal Scientific Journal, Specialised Magazine, local radio:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-hydrogen-energy>

<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/hydrogen>

<https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2023/07/230713142013.htm>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-hydrogen-energy> (International Journal of Hydrogen Energy)

<https://thehydrogenstandard.com/> (The Hydrogen Standards)

<https://h2-international.com/> (H2 International)

<https://revolve.media/magazine/> (REVOLVE Media magazine) 29

<https://www.ilsole24ore.com> (Il Sole24Ore)

<https://www.radio24.ilsole24ore.com> (Radio24 – Il Sole24Ore)

http://www.nuova-energia.com/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=44&Itemid=74 (Nuova Energia)

<https://www.rivistaenergia.it/la-rivista/> (Energia)

Local events:

<https://www.centroscienza.it/settimanedellascienza/> (Le Settimane della Scienza, Italy – Torino, every spring)

An update on the dissemination activities will be made during the consortium General Assembly meetings and all dissemination activities will be kept in the dedicated monitoring file for reporting purposes.

7.2 Online engagement indicators

Below an explanation of the terminology used to track the impact of online content:

- Delivery Rate = number of emails delivered/number of emails sent (measured in percentage);
- Open Rate = number of emails opened/number of emails delivered (measured in percentage);
- Opt-out Rate = number of unsubscribes/number of emails opened (measured in percentage);
- Click to delivery rate = number of clicks in the email/number of emails delivered (measured in percentage);
- Response Rate = Total number of first time responses/total number of emails opened.

7.3 SNs and online engagement indicators

TOOLS	DATA
Google Analytics 4	Unique visitors on the project website Total visits on the project website
Facebook and Instagram Insights	Likes, unlikes, engagement, reach
LinkedIn statistics	LinkedIn followers
Twitter Analytics	Twitter impressions New followers, Nr. Tweets, Impressions, Link clicks, Retweets, Favourites, Replies, Mention
YouTube counter	YouTube views

Table 8: Tools and metrics to measure KPIs

7.4 Offline engagement indicators

Quantitative Analysis

- Quantity and quality of submissions/participations;
- Former engaged stakeholder vs. novel engaged stakeholder.

Qualitative Analysis

- Stakeholder satisfaction;
- Community Building, in terms of established collaborations;
- Awareness raising, in terms of HYPOP SNs subscribers after the event;
- Cost effectiveness, in terms of effort used compared to the above-mentioned indicators;
- Performance improvements.

7.5 Barriers and obstacles to reach KPIs

The potential barriers to dissemination and communication related to the main actions foreseen are identified in Table 9:

Tools, activities, channels	Metrics	Barriers and obstacles
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of visits, time spent on the website and returning visitors; • Number of countries; website contents shared by visitors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners do not promote in their channels the website • Other EU projects and initiatives do not reshare news and contents through their channels • Limited number of information sources trusted/preferred
Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of downloads • Articles realised by entities external to the consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low confidence in the quality of the information provided • Unclear utility and relevance for users • Non-user-friendly format
Social Networks (SNs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of followers, engagement rates (via SNs analytics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited capacity to reach intended users • Project results presented in language not adapted and/or not accessible to the different target groups • Limited attractiveness of the information
Events and conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numbers of events • Number of attendees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too many events focused on similar contents • Restriction to the participation on on-site events • Participants do not see added value of the event

Table 9: Barriers and obstacleOs to reach KPIs

These barriers could be overcome by a clear definition of the target groups that HYPOP wants to reach and engage, defining the content in a way that is really attractive to them. Additionally, the management structure developed for the involvement of all partners in the process of dissemination and communication activities should assure the achievement of the KPIs.

8 Communication and dissemination management structure

8.1 Partners' responsibilities

APRE, leader of the WP5, is responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication strategy; moreover, it is in charge for the development of the main tools and graphic materials that will be used during the project.

Each partner will:

- Contribute to the communication and dissemination strategy implementation;
- Engage new stakeholders in their network and encourage cooperation with them;
- Ensure the control of the quality of the activities implemented.

All HYPOP partners will be actively involved in the implementation of communication and dissemination activities. More specifically, the expected contributions from partners are the following:

- Implementing dissemination activities in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploiting their contacts, networks and channels;
- Supplying news and updates for the web portal and newsletter via the form available on the project repository;
- Helping to keep the project's Social Media Accounts (SMAs) alive and active, in particular supporting the development of contents to be communicated;
- Participating to conferences, workshops, events etc. in order to promote the project and its outcomes.

8.2 Procedures and reporting

Monitoring will be carried out by each partner on a regular basis through an online report template uploaded on the project repository.

The communication and dissemination strategy will undergo an update at M12. Through continuous monitoring, HYPOP will be able to continuously measure its performance, key impacts and propose corrective actions to improve performance and maximise impacts, if needed, thus adopting a fully scalable approach to its Communication and Dissemination strategy.

Measurement of impacts and outreach will be guaranteed by the consolidated monitoring report, involving both the online, social media channels and the engagement activities as described in the Technical Annex to the Grant Agreement.

Monitoring activities will be carried out on a regular basis and its outcomes will be included in D.5.3 *Communication and Dissemination Activities Report* (M12, updated M24). This deliverable will also contain a section dedicated to the updated information of this Strategy, if any.

Regarding project and initiatives cooperation, its monitoring will be inserted into the D5.5 *Networking with other projects and initiatives report* (M12, updated M24).

In order to guarantee the effective involvement of all partners in the communication and dissemination activities, procedures concerning reporting activities and for contributing to the activities were defined.

An online spreadsheet was created in order to track all the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners. It contains two different sheets, one for communication activities and one for dissemination ones. In depth, each sheet contains:

Dissemination activities	Communication activities
Partner	Partner
WP	WP
Dissemination activity name	Task
Date	Communication activity name
Type of activity	Description
Target audience	Target audience
Description of objectives with reference to specific project output	Outcome
Link/website	Status
Status of the activity	Link/website
# of people reached	# of people reached

Table 10: communication and dissemination required fields

9 Timeline

YEAR 1		SNs animation
M	Activities	
M1	Definition of project logo and HYPOP visual identity	
M2	Production of templates and communication toolkit	
M3	D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	
M4	D5.2 Visual Identity Handbook	
M5	HYPOP splash page, definition of website pages (II)	
M6	Website and social media channels opened and online, D5.5 Strategic exploitation Plan, Creation of common repository space for HYPOP materials, Communication toolkit available online for Partners	
M7		
M8	Newsletter #1, social media campaign #1, video/infographic #1	
M9		
M10		
M11	Social media campaign #2	
M12	5.3 Communication and Dissemination Activities Report, D5.4 Networking with other projects and initiatives Report, 5.6 Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan updated	
YEAR 2		SNs animation
M13		
M14	Social media campaign #3	
M15		
M16	Newsletter #2, video/infographic #2	
M17	Social media campaign #3	
M18	D5.8 Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan updated	
M19		
M20	Social media campaign #4	
M21		
M22		
M23	Social media campaign #5	
M24	Newsletter #3, video/infographic #3, D5.6 Communication and Dissemination Report updated, 5.8 Communication and Dissemination Activities Report, D5.9 Networking with other projects and initiatives Report, 5.10 Strategic Exploitation Plan	

10 Exploitation of the results

An efficient exploitation of results is a key premise for enhancing the project’s outcomes and impacts after its end. Aim of the upscaling is to expand and allow replication of the co-created activities and results to reach more actors and broaden the effectiveness of the activities. The scaling up strategy will ensure at first the transferability (assured through the associated partner regions). Further, the strategy will decide about types of scaling up, either on a quantitative basis (increasing the numbers of networks, regions, actors), on a functional level (by increasing the effectiveness) or on a political/organisational level (applying activities on a different level). The upscaling approach will be combined with strategic choices in the areas of dissemination but also the organisational process (integration of regions, networks), costs and mobilization of resources as well as monitoring and evaluation to measure the impact of the scaling activity.

The exploitable assets that will emerge from HYPOP activities will be shared with the aim of maximising the project impact and systematically plan for its exploitation beyond its lifetime. The following table shows the exploitable assets, and highlights the deliverables and Work Packages they refer to, as well as the partner overall responsible for them:

Title	WP(s)	Responsible partner
Stakeholder database	WP5/WP6	ENVI
HYPOP website	WP5	APRE
Recommendations, Guidelines, Best Practices	WP3/WP4	ENVI
Public Information Strategy	WP5	APRE
Graphic and informative materials: videos, infographics	WP5	APRE
Stakeholders’ requirements reports	WP2	ENVI
Outputs from hydrogen public opinion survey	WP1	IMI
S-LCA material	WP3	IME

Table 11: List of project exploitable assets

Exploitation activities will be compliant with the Data Management Plan (DMP) (D6.2) and also with the Consortium Agreement signed by partners [Article 8.1 “Ownership of results” *Results are owned by the Party that generates them*]. Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results [Consortium Agreement, Article 8.1 – “Joint ownership”].

11 Annexes

11.1 Communication and Dissemination Toolkit

11.1.1 Brand Manual

project key words

KEY WORDS

- ^ hydrogen
- ^ technology - information
- ^ public - inclusive
usable - attractive -
reassure - popular - collaboration
- ^ progress - improvement

Clean Hydrogen Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

11.1.2 Logo

logo concept

In this logo proposal the first element "H" immediately, and unconsciously, identifies the protagonist of the project: Hydrogen, also referred to by the symbology used to represent the letter "O" of the POP writing. There is a strong reference to the pop art style, in a modern key, and the graphic elements inserted to obtain this style represent some of the key elements of the project.

logo anatomy

HYPOP logo is a combination mark :

Pictogram (Logo Mark) + Wordmark + Payoff

Each part of the logo can be used alone or composed, in this way there is great flexibility for different applications.

Pictogram/Favicon

Wordmark

Payoff
(if you want to include the pay off this is the right position)

Let's make the hydrogen revolution

logo versions - official colors - white

HORIZONTAL

WEB USE

PICTOGRAM

FAVICON

logo versions - official color - dark background

HORIZONTAL

WEB USE

PICTOGRAM

FAVICON

logo versions - monochromatic - dark background

HORIZONTAL

WEB USE

PICTOGRAM

logo versions - monochromatic - light background

logo dimension & propositions - safety area

Safety area ensures that external elements are not interfering in the mark readability. It should be always respected this margin corresponding to the height of the character "Y".

logo dimension & propositions - minimum size

Minimum dimensions to ensure the readability of the mark.

Printed media:

The minimum size for the logo is 35 mm width for the official version or 20 mm width for the vertical version. For sizes below this measures only the pictogram, up to 10 mm, must be used. Below 10 mm must be used just the wordmark "HYPOP".

Digital formats:

The minimum size for the logo is 220 px width for the official version or 120 px width for the vertical version. For sizes below this measures only the pictogram, up to 60 px, must be used. Below 60 px must be used just the wordmark "HYPOP".

writing project naming

Always write the project name:
HYPOP

HYPOP ✓ Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullamco laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute irure reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. **HYPOP** ✗ excepteur sint obcaecat cupiditat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

HyPop ✗ Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullamco laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute irure reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. **hyPop** ✗ excepteur sint obcaecat cupiditat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

selected fonts

MAIN FONT

Lexend Exa font family

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890
'?""!""(%)[#{@}]/&\<-+÷x=>
©\$€£¥¢;,:,*

For this project are used three fonts:

- **Lexend Exa font Family** only for graphic materials (Title)
- **Proxima Nova font Family** only for graphic materials (Body text)
- **Lato font Family** for common documents and plain text

Lexend Exa - semibold

Proxima Nova - regular

LOREM IPSUM

dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Lexend Exa - semibold

Proxima Nova - regular

LOREM IPSUM

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat

11.1.3 Website and SNs

Figure 1: website tree

Figure 2: website home

Figure 3: website video section

Figure 4: website results section

Join our community!

Database/ Newsletter Subscription

This consent form is designed to collect expressions of interest to be part of HYPOP's Community and to receive the HYPOP's newsletters.

The newsletter subscription will result in invitations to events and workshops, relevant initiatives and activities.

HYPOP's partners ensure that processing activities will take place in compliance with Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

First name

Last name

Organization

Country

E-Mail

Website

Category

- Citizens
- EU and local projects
- Manufactures/Hydrogen sector
- HYPOP Identified stakeholders
- Clusters, territorial associations, networks, hydrogen valley
- First responders
- Permitting Authorities
- Certification Bodies
- Experts on Hydrogen and Communication
- Public authorities (decision-makers)
- Scientific Community
- Other

Select your registration option(s)

- Newsletter only
- HYPOP Stakeholders database
- HYPOP Stakeholders database and newsletter

I agree with the Privacy Policy and authorize HYPOP to store my data, and to answer to my contact request.

SUBSCRIBE

Figure 5: website Join our Community section

Figure 6: website news and updates section

Figure 7: Facebook profile

Figure 8: LinkedIn profile

Figure 9: Twitter/X profile

Figure 10: Instagram profile

Figure 11: YouTube channel

Figure 12: example of card to be posted on social media channels

<p>HY POP</p> <p>1 Introduction</p> <p>Here you put the deliverable introduction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 2 3 <p>7</p>	<p>HY POP</p> <p>2 Section</p> <p>8</p>	<p>HY POP</p> <p>3 Section</p> <p>3.1 Subsection</p> <p>This is the second level section. Add the text.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bullet Level One <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bullet Level Two Bullet Level Three <p>3.1.1 Subsubsection</p> <p>This is the 3rd level section. Add the text ex: www.hypop-project.eu</p> <p>3.2 Subsection</p> <p>This is the second level section. Add the text.</p> <p>9</p>
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<p>HY POP</p> <p>Table Reference:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>TEST</td> <td>TEST</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>TEST</td> </tr> <tr> <td>TEST</td> <td></td> <td>TEST</td> <td>TEST</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>TEST</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <p>Figure Reference:</p> <p>Figure 1</p> <p>10</p>	TEST	TEST			TEST	TEST		TEST	TEST		TEST					<p>HY POP</p> <p>4 Conclusions</p> <p>Here you summarize the conclusions.</p> <p>11</p>	<p>HY POP</p> <p>5 Appendix A</p> <p>Here you may put appendices, if any.</p> <p>12</p>
TEST	TEST			TEST													
TEST		TEST	TEST														
TEST																	

HYPOP

6 References

Please put the references in alphabetical order following the examples shown below.

General Reference:
SurnameAuthor J.K., SurnameAuthor2 K., YEAR. Title of the article/book/etc... Publisher/Editorial. Vol.X, pages XXX-XX

13

HYPOP

7 Landscape

14

HYPOP

15

HYPOP

www.hypop-project.eu
info@hypop-project.eu

#HYPOPPROJECT

Let's make the hydrogen revolution

Logos: ENVIRONMENT Fairs, IMI, idea energy, APRE, H, R, TUEV, TWeD, Clean Hydrogen Partnership, EU

11.1.4.2 PowerPoint template

EDIT KICKER

TITLE

Fare clic per inserire testo

Project HYPOP - GA nr. 101111933

EDIT KICKER

TITLE

TITLE

Fare clic per inserire testo

Fare clic per inserire testo

Project HYPOP - GA nr. 101111933

EDIT KICKER

TITLE

Fare clic per inserire testo

Project HYPOP - GA nr. 101111933

• Fare clic sull'icona per inserire un'immagine

EDIT KICKER

Salvato in questo PC

TITLE

Fare clic per inserire testo

Project HYPOP - GA nr. 101111933

• Fare clic sull'icona per inserire un'immagine

NAME OF PRESENTER

ORGANIZATION

email

phone

relevant details

Thank you for your attention!

www.hypop-project.eu

info@hypop-project.eu

#HYPOP

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Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Clean Hydrogen Partnership. Neither the European Union nor the Clean Hydrogen Partnership can be held responsible for them.

Hy POP

Join us!

Let's make the hydrogen revolution

HYPOP's GOAL

HYPOP aims to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits. Through the understanding of public perception and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies, HYPOP will provide citizens, consumers and end-users with guidelines and knowledge to increase their trust in hydrogen and its implementation in daily life.

HYPOP's ACTIVITIES

HYPOP will work to pursue its objective to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through the following activities:

- the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of Hydrogen technologies
- the creation of a social platform collecting communication materials (videos, news, scientific papers) on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities
- the definition of indicators to be used for Hydrogen Social Life Cycle Assessment for public acceptance and informed decision-making.

HYPOP will focus on two applications:
residential and mobility, which will enter into the daily life of people.

www.hypop-project.eu
info@hypop-project.eu
#HYPOPPROJECT

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ENVIROMENT PARK
IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCE
INNOVATION

IMI
Institute for Methods Innovation

idea energy

APRE

Hidrógeno

REGIONALNA IZBA GOŠPOTINAZA POKROBILCA

TWeD

BILBAO HYDROGEN CLUSTER

Clean Hydrogen Partnership

Co-funded by the European Union

11.1.6 Roll Up

Hy POP

Let's make the hydrogen revolution

HYPOP will provide citizens, consumers and end-users with guidelines and knowledge to increase their trust in hydrogen and its implementation in daily life.

Join us!

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#HYPOPPROJECT

Clean Hydrogen Partnership
Co-funded by the European Union

ENVIRONMENT PARK

IMI Institute for Materials and Manufacturing

idea

APRE

TWeD

IZBA

WILKAR HYDROGEN GALLERY

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11.1.7 Virtual Background

 www.hypop-project.eu

 info@hypop-project.eu

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Let's make
the hydrogen
revolution

